

New model for estimating trophic position in mammalian carnivores based on bone collagen individual amino acids nitrogen stable isotopes

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ABSTRACT

Trophic position, or the level occupied by an organism in the food chain, is a key characteristic for understanding its role in the recent or past ecosystem. Nitrogen stable isotopes in selected amino acids of bone collagen, in particular in the glutamate and phenylalanine, allow for quantification of the trophic position in fossils and thus, for reconstruction of the ecological history of species and landscapes. Applying this method for carnivorous mammals was limited until now due to the lack of a key parameter, the trophic discrimination factor (TDF) for collagen, representing an isotopic shift in amino acids from prey bone collagen to carnivore bone collagen. In this study, we determined this parameter in two carnivorans: the modern wolf and the Pleistocene cave hyena. We measured the glutamate and phenylalanine $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ values in bone collagen of these carnivores and their prey, applying five models to estimate the mean diet. We proposed a new model of calculating the TDF for collagen-based data, with herbivores regarded as a baseline level. We found collagen-to-collagen glutamate-phenylalanine TDF in both studied carnivorans and in all models of the mean diet similar to each other, +4.8 ‰ on average. This value is lower than that determined previously in invertebrate proteins or in plant-to-vertebrate tissue systems. Our results allow for more accurate reconstruction of trophic position in carnivores, including paleontological and archaeological materials where bone collagen is the only available tissue. We applied our new herbivore model and collagen-based TDF to re-assess the trophic structure of an exemplary Late Pleistocene assemblage, and found that the Upper Paleolithic humans at this site occupied a higher trophic position than previously determined.

1. Introduction

Estimation of the trophic position (TP) of an animal within the food web is one of the most powerful implementations of stable isotopes in paleoecology. Common applications include ecology and ecosystems conservation, where isotopes provide an insight into the evolution of ecosystems in a diachronic view (DeNiro and Epstein, 1981; Hofman-Kamińska et al., 2019; Kubiak et al., 2021; Rosengren and Magnell, 2024); paleontology, where it opens possibilities for the reconstruction of extinct taxa ecology (Bocherens, 2015; Bocherens et al., 2011; Krajcarz et al., 2016; Krajcarz et al., 2023; Tejada et al., 2021); and

archaeology and paleoanthropology, where stable isotopes allow for tracking the habits and the place of our ancestors in past ecosystems (Colonese et al., 2014; Drucker et al., 2015; Fontanals-Coll et al., 2023; Larson and Fuller, 2014; Naito et al., 2016a; Soncin et al., 2021; Wißing et al., 2016).

Nitrogen isotopic composition in collagen is widely used as a proxy of TP due to distinct fractionation of ^{15}N and ^{14}N isotopes along the trophic chain (e.g., plants, or TP 1 → herbivores, or TP 2 → primary carnivores, or TP 3 → secondary carnivores, or TP 4, etc.) (Bocherens, 2000; Caut et al., 2009; Ishikawa, 2018; Martínez Del Rio et al., 2009; Minagawa and Wada, 1984). This isotopic shift between a consumer's

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diet and its body tissue (i.e., between TP X and TP X + 1) is used as quantified parameter, known as a trophic discrimination factor (TDF) (Bocherens and Drucker, 2003; Caut et al., 2009; Krajcarz et al., 2018) and applied in numerical modelling to track detailed trophic relationships between individuals and taxa (Bocherens, 2015; Bocherens et al., 2015; Newsome et al., 2007; Wißing et al., 2019). Isotopic fractionation is shaped by physiology and isotopic composition of the diet, and it also differs according to phylogenetic group, individual, and between different tissues (Caut et al., 2009; Karlson et al., 2024; Layman and Post, 2008; Martínez Del Rio et al., 2009; Post, 2002; Stephens et al., 2023; Vanderklift and Ponsard, 2003). Therefore, it is extremely important to understand the complexities of the isotope flow between the prey's and predator's collagen in phylogenetic and ecologic groups of animals that are of particular interest.

The bulk collagen $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ values (the average $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ of the entire collagen fraction) are widely applied in paleodietary studies; nevertheless, it has important interpretative limitations (Larsen et al., 2022; Whiteman et al., 2021; Yun et al., 2022). These come from variable $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ values among primary producers (plants), which is an effect of plant physiology and biotope conditions (Barnett, 1994; Craine et al., 2015; Männel et al., 2007; Ramirez et al., 2021; Santesteban et al., 2024; Wang and Wooller, 2006). Therefore, herbivores feeding on isotopically different plants may exhibit different $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ values, and consequently be mistakenly attributed to TPs. The way to overcome the problem of isotopic variability in producers is the analysis of the $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ values in individual amino acids (AAs) isolated from fossil collagen (Chikaraishi et al., 2009, 2011; Fogel et al., 1997; Hare et al., 1991; Ishikawa, 2018; Larsen et al., 2022; McMahon et al., 2015; Ohkouchi, 2023; Styring et al., 2010; Yun et al., 2022). The advantage of this method comes from individual and specific rate of fractionation in each AA (i.e., different TDFs in particular AAs). Essential AAs are known in isotopic ecology as 'source AAs', i.e., they exhibit no or limited fractionation from dietary source to tissue of the consumer; remaining non-essential' AA's, called 'trophic AAs', undergo more or less distinct fractionation along the trophic chain (Hebert et al., 2016; McCarthy et al., 2007; Nielsen et al., 2015; O'Connell, 2017; Ohkouchi, 2023; Popp et al., 2007). Ecological and paleoecological studies usually focus on phenylalanine (Phe) as a 'source AA', and glutamate (Glx; a sum of glutamic acid and glutamine) as a 'trophic AA' (Larsen et al., 2022; O'Connell, 2017; Ohkouchi, 2023; Yun et al., 2022). The difference between diet-to-body fractionation rates in these AAs is known as Glu-Phe trophic discrimination factor ($\text{TDF}_{\text{Glu-Phe}}$), calculated as:

$$\text{TDF}_{\text{Glu-Phe}} = \Delta^{15}\text{N}_{\text{Glx}} - \Delta^{15}\text{N}_{\text{Phe}} \quad (1)$$

where $\Delta^{15}\text{N}_{\text{Glx}}$ and $\Delta^{15}\text{N}_{\text{Phe}}$ are differences between $\delta^{15}\text{N}_{\text{Glx}}$ or $\delta^{15}\text{N}_{\text{Phe}}$ of neighboring trophic levels, respectively. The TP is then derived from the difference of the studied consumer's $\delta^{15}\text{N}_{\text{Glx}}$ and $\delta^{15}\text{N}_{\text{Phe}}$ divided by the $\text{TDF}_{\text{Glx-Phe}}$; it is therefore independent from absolute $\delta^{15}\text{N}_{\text{Glx}}$ and $\delta^{15}\text{N}_{\text{Phe}}$ values, but relates to the ratio between them. To anchor the TP estimation formula at the food web baseline, the $\delta^{15}\text{N}_{\text{Glx}} - \delta^{15}\text{N}_{\text{Phe}}$ difference in plants is also needed. This parameter is known as β (beta) (Chikaraishi et al., 2009, 2010; Ramirez et al., 2021). The TP estimation follows the formula:

$$\text{TP} = (\delta^{15}\text{N}_{\text{Glx}} - \delta^{15}\text{N}_{\text{Phe}} - \beta) / \text{TDF}_{\text{Glx-Phe}} + 1 \quad (2)$$

This formula attributes a numerical value to the TP of an individual as follows: TP = 2, a primary consumer (a herbivore); TP = 3, a secondary consumer (a carnivore feeding on herbivores); TP = 4, a tertiary consumer (a carnivore feeding on TP3 carnivores), etc. Intermediate values refer to a mixed diet. The formula needs two variables ($\delta^{15}\text{N}_{\text{Glx}}$ and $\delta^{15}\text{N}_{\text{Phe}}$), which are measured in a studied specimen; and two parameters, i.e., β and $\text{TDF}_{\text{Glx-Phe}}$, which are usually arbitrarily assigned. The β values were established for C₃ terrestrial plants, C₄ terrestrial plants, and marine algae (Chikaraishi et al., 2009, 2010, 2011). The $\text{TDF}_{\text{Glx-Phe}}$ value has been determined for several terrestrial and aquatic

animals, and stays in a range between 5 ‰ and 9 ‰ (Chikaraishi et al., 2009, 2010, 2011; Steffan et al., 2013). Paleoecological studies usually use a value of +7.6 ‰ (Choy et al., 2024; Jaouen et al., 2019; Naito et al., 2016a; Naito et al., 2016b; Nakashita et al., 2011). This value is an average for aquatic and terrestrial animals of variable TPs and from variable phylogenetic groups and it is commonly regarded as a constant although it has been suggested to be likely overestimated (Nielsen et al., 2015; Yun et al., 2022).

While the actual value has a huge impact on the TP estimations, it is noteworthy that the $\text{TDF}_{\text{Glx-Phe}}$ was never established for collagen-to-collagen fractionation. For vertebrates, the only few taxon-related $\text{TDF}_{\text{Glx-Phe}}$ values determined usually concern the total protein pool of the diet and blood and/or muscle of the consumer (Dale et al., 2011; Germain et al., 2013; Lorrain et al., 2009; Popp et al., 2007; Whiteman et al., 2021). Moreover, many studies raised the issue of possible variation among the TDFs, due to phylogenetic and physiological differences, type of tissues studied, and diet quality (Besser et al., 2022; Choi et al., 2020; Dale et al., 2011; Germain et al., 2013; Lorrain et al., 2009; McMahon et al., 2015; Nielsen et al., 2015; O'Connell, 2017; Post, 2002; Yun et al., 2022). To address these concerns, we designed a new study presented here. The primary objective of this study was to provide the missing data on the prey collagen-to-predator collagen $\text{TDF}_{\text{Glx-Phe}}$ for terrestrial mammalian carnivores. To achieve this goal, we analyzed the $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ values of individual AAs (Glx and Phe) in bone collagen of two terrestrial carnivores and their prey. We focused on recent wolf from the Białowieża Primeval Forest (eastern Poland), whose hunting preferences are well known due the intense ecological monitoring (Jędrzejewski et al., 2000); and Pleistocene cave hyena from Perspektywiczna Cave (southern Poland), whose diet was previously studied through proteomic taxonomy of digested bone fragments (Krajcarz et al., 2025).

2. Material and methods

2.1. Sample selection

The collagen-to-collagen TDF studies are challenging. First, they require bone samples of the predator and its prey, which is difficult to obtain and raises ethical concerns. Second, the data about the diet composition is needed, which is easy to achieve under controlled lab conditions, but such conditions can impact animal physiology and thus do not represent well the natural isotopic relationships (Caut et al., 2009). To overcome these difficulties, we focused on two collections of bones from natural settings that were previously used to establish bulk collagen $\Delta^{13}\text{C}$ and $\Delta^{15}\text{N}$ TDFs (Bocherens and Drucker, 2003; Krajcarz et al., 2025; Krajcarz et al., 2023):

- 1) bones of recent wolf and its prey from the Białowieża Primeval Forest (Poland, Fig. S1). The studied individuals died between 1969 and 2011, and were collected by and stored at the Scientific Zoological Collection in Mammal Research Institute, Polish Academy of Sciences in Białowieża (Poland).
- 2) collection of bones of the Pleistocene cave hyena and its prey from Perspektywiczna Cave (Poland, Fig. S1). The bones were collected during archaeological excavation in 2012–2018 and stored at the Institute of Archaeology, Nicolaus Copernicus University in Toruń (Poland).

Samples were collected from variable (Białowieża Primeval Forest) or unidentified (hyena den) skeleton elements. Previous studies shown that the intra-individual differences in bone collagen $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ are neglectable, regardless of the skeletal element (Sykut et al., 2020; Hyland et al., 2022).

2.2. Diet composition

The estimation of the proportion of prey species in the wolf diet was based on long-term ecological monitoring in the Białowieża Forest (Jędrzejewski et al., 2000), where our material was collected. Diet (prey) composition for the wolves was estimated in several ways: scat composition, number of kills, and predation impact (details are presented in Supplementary Text); likewise, we provided three models of wolf diet composition (models W1, W2, and W3; details are presented in Supplementary Text and the supplementary Tables S3–S5).

The proportion of prey species in hyena diet was based on ZooMS identification of digested bone fragments (Krajcarz et al., 2025). Following the methodology presented therein, we transformed the number of each taxon's bone fragments into the consumed biomass of that taxon, after Ackerman et al. (1984), which uses the average body mass of each taxon and its digestibility. We provide two models: model H1 including the prey body mass only; and model H2 including both the body mass and the digestibility (details are presented in the Supplementary Text and supplementary Tables S6–S7; for discussion of model limitations see Krajcarz et al., 2025).

2.3. Collagen samples

We used collagen extracts from previous studies (Bocherens and Drucker, 2003; Krajcarz et al., 2023, 2025) and the collagen extraction procedure is presented herein. Due to time consuming procedures of sample preparation and measurements, we have limited the number of samples ($N = 43$). Details of the samples are presented in the supplementary Tables S3–S7.

2.4. Reference standards

We used a mixture of 15 synthetic AAs of known isotopic composition (cross-checked through EA-IRMS in two independent labs: the Geoecology Working Group of the University of Tübingen, Tübingen, Germany; and the Institute of Geological Sciences of the Polish Academy of Sciences, Warsaw, Poland) as a reference standard. Details are presented in the Supplementary Text. The reference materials used for EA-IRMS calibration were: USGS-40, USGS-41a, USGS-65, USGS-88, USGS-89, and IAEA-600.

As an internal standard added to each sample and a blank, we used L-norleucine from Sigma-Aldrich (Nle , $\delta^{15}\text{N} = -1.96 \pm 0.17 \text{‰}$), prepared through dissolution of 18.88 mg of Nle in 50 mL of 0.1 M HCl. The same Nle was also included in the 15 AAs reference standard.

2.5. AAs derivatization

Samples of collagen of around 1–2 mg were hydrolyzed in 1 ml of 6 M HCl at 110 °C for 20 h. 100 μl of the internal standard solution was added to each sample prior the hydrolysis. The hydrolysates were centrifuged (12,800 RPM, 6-cm radius centrifuge for 1 min) using Pall Nanosep filters (0.45 μm) and defatted in hexane-dichloromethane (DCM) mix (3:2, v:v). The hydrolyzed AAs were dried at 60 °C under a gentle stream of N_2 and derivatized to form *N*-acetyl-isopropyl (NAIP) esters according to Corr et al. (2007). Details are presented in the Supplementary Text. The steps of hydrolysis, filtration with Pall Nanosep filters, and hexane/DCM defatting were omitted for reference standards.

2.6. GC-C-IRMS setup

Gas chromatography–combustion–isotope ratio mass spectrometry (GC-C-IRMS) measurements were performed at the facilities of the Biogeology Working Group, Department of Geosciences of the University of Tübingen (Germany) using a gas chromatograph (HP 7890B, Agilent Technologies, US) connected to a furnace (GC5 Interface, Elementar, Germany) with hybrid oxidation-reduction reactor (GC5

furnace tube, Elementar), and an isotope ratio mass spectrometer (Iso-prime 100, Elementar). Samples dissolved in isopropyl acetate were injected in a splitless mode at 250 °C and separated on an Agilent VF-23 ms column (60 m length, 0.32 mm diameter, 0.25 μm film thickness). The oven starting temperature was 70 °C for 0.5 min and then increased at a rate of 15 °C/min to 130 °C, a rate of 2 °C/min to 175 °C, a rate of 1 °C/min to 185 °C, a rate of 2 °C/min to 225 °C (1 min hold), and a rate of 20 °C/min to 255 °C (5 min hold). The carrier gas (He) flow rate was 1.5 ml/min. The combustion reactor with NiCr, Cu, and Pt wires was held at 950 °C.

2.7. $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ measurements and corrections

All samples were measured in triplicate. Additional replicate(s) were analyzed if initial measurements fell outside the expected standard deviation (SD) range of $\pm 1 \text{‰}$. A reference standard was run before and after every triplicate. We used the IonVantage control software (Iso-prime) dedicated to our IRMS model and LyticOS software (Elementar) to map or integrate AA peaks in chromatograms and determine their isotopic values.

The $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ raw values were corrected versus Nle internal standard and scale-normalized to the 15 AAs reference standard (Leu, Ile, Nle, Met, and Lys were not included in the normalization; see the Supplementary Text for explanation) according to (Yarnes and Herszage, 2017). Nitrogen isotope ratios were reported as $\delta^{15}\text{N} \text{‰}$ relative to the average value of atmospheric nitrogen AIR N_2 , assuming that the expected values of the 15 AAs reference standard and the Nle referred to the AIR N_2 , due to the use of international certified reference materials during their EA-IRMS check.

2.8. TDF calculation

Our calculations followed the method presented by Krajcarz et al. (2025). First, we obtained the average isotopic composition of Glx and Phe of the carnivore and those of its mean diet, separately for each mean diet model. Then, Glx and Phe individual TDFs ($\Delta^{15}\text{N}_{\text{Glx}}$ and $\Delta^{15}\text{N}_{\text{Phe}}$) were calculated as differences between carnivore's mean isotopic value and its modeled mean diet isotopic values. Finally, the $\text{TDF}_{\text{Glx-Phe}}$ was calculated as a difference between $\Delta^{15}\text{N}_{\text{Glx}}$ and $\Delta^{15}\text{N}_{\text{Phe}}$ for a given carnivore. The details and equations are presented in the Supplementary Text. All calculations were performed in the MS Excel software. The spreadsheets are available in the supplementary Tables S3–S7.

2.9. Statistics

We used basic statistics tests: Pearson's correlation for testing the correlation between data of normal distribution; Spearman's D correlation for testing the correlation between data of not normal distribution; linear fit model for testing the reliability of linear regression; and ANCOVA to compare two linear regressions. All tests were performed in PAST software, version 4.05 (Hammer et al., 2001).

3. Results

3.1. Glx and Phe $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ values

We identified $\delta^{15}\text{N}_{\text{Glx}}$ and $\delta^{15}\text{N}_{\text{Phe}}$ paired values in wolf *Canis lupus* individuals ($n = 6$) and their prey: red deer *Cervus elaphus* ($n = 8$), roe deer *Capreolus capreolus* ($n = 6$), European bison *Bison bonasus* ($n = 1$), and wild boar *Sus scrofa* ($n = 3$); and in cave hyena *Crocuta crocuta* individuals ($n = 4$) and their prey: mammoth *Mammuthus primigenius* ($n = 3$), woolly rhinoceros *Coelodonta antiquitatis* ($n = 3$), steppe bison *Bison priscus* ($n = 3$), horse *Equus ferus* ($n = 3$), and reindeer *Rangifer tarandus* ($n = 3$) (data available from the Zenodo digital repository <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14795699>). Quality control parameters of our collagen extracts and AAs isotopic determination were within

acceptable ranges (Figs. S2 and S3 in the Supplementary Text). Pleistocene animals had higher $\delta^{15}\text{N}_{\text{Glx}}$ and $\delta^{15}\text{N}_{\text{Phe}}$ values than the modern ones (Table 1, Fig. 1), both in herbivores and in carnivores. This likely represents different productivity of ecosystems and/or different soil and climatic conditions, as productive and arid steppes typically exhibit higher $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ signals in soils, vegetation, and consumers, due to greater nitrogen cycling and faster removal of ^{14}N from the geoecosystem (Ambrose, 1991; Amundson et al., 2003; Schwartz-Narbonne et al., 2015, 2019).

3.2. Glx and Phe $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ TDF

Despite this difference, the diet collagen-to-carnivore collagen ^{15}N enrichments in both Glx and Phe ($\Delta^{15}\text{N}_{\text{Glx}}$ and $\Delta^{15}\text{N}_{\text{Phe}}$, respectively) were similar between two carnivores (Fig. 1). We calculated several independent $\text{TDF}_{\text{Glx-Phe}}$ values (Table 1) for different models of the mean diet estimation (details are presented in the Supplementary Text). We found the collagen-to-collagen $\text{TDF}_{\text{Glx-Phe}}$ in our five models and in both carnivores similar to each other and highly overlapping within their SE ranges, all between $+4.3\text{‰}$ and $+5.3\text{‰}$ AIR N_2 . (Table 1). The average collagen-to-collagen $\text{TDF}_{\text{Glx-Phe}}$ for all models for wolf and hyena was $+4.8 \pm 0.1$.

4. Discussion

4.1. Collagen-to-collagen TDF and other tissue-specific TDFs

Many studies suggested that the commonly applied $+7.6\text{‰}$ value of $\text{TDF}_{\text{Glx-Phe}}$ in vertebrates may be overestimated (Dale et al., 2011; Germain et al., 2013; Lorrain et al., 2009; Popp et al., 2007; Whiteman et al., 2021). Meta-analysis of numerous data by (Nielsen et al., 2015) pointed toward $+6.6\text{‰}$, while field studies on vertebrates evidenced even lower values, closer to around $+4\text{‰}$ (Germain et al., 2013; Lorrain et al., 2009). It was also suggested that TDF would be lower for more protein-rich diet; e.g., the results of experimental feeding studies revealed consumers feeding on high protein diets had lower TDF values than consumers feeding on low quality diets (McMahon et al., 2015; Whiteman et al., 2021), i.e., for $\text{TP} > 2$. Our collagen-to-collagen $\text{TDF}_{\text{Glx-Phe}}$ values between 4.6 ± 0.3 and 5.0 ± 0.3 (Table 1), found in wolf and hyena, are close to these predictions.

Our TDFs were built on data for animals that are predominantly secondary consumers, i.e., that are around $\text{TP} = 3$. It is highly possible that collagen-to-collagen TDFs for higher TP carnivores (i.e., $\text{TP} > 3$) are likely to be similar, due to similar quality of the meat-based diet. For herbivores, no analogous collagen-to-collagen TDF can be established, because herbivores do not include collagen-bearing food sources in their diet. In case of herbivores, the plant protein-to-herbivore collagen TDF makes sense in paleoecology, but it needs further study. We cautiously predict this TDF to be similar to the ones determined for modern plant protein pool-herbivore protein pool in other animals (Chikaraishi et al., 2009, 2010, 2011).

Table 1

Diet collagen-to-carnivore collagen $\text{TDF}_{\text{Glx-Phe}}$ for wolf and hyena. Bone collagen glutamate and phenylalanine $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ values (mean \pm standard error) are provided for the studied carnivores and their diet estimated through several models (for calculation method see the Supplementary Text and supplementary Tables S3–S7). Related Glx-Phe trophic discrimination factors (mean \pm standard error) represent differences between carnivore and its prey isotopic values.

Carnivore	model of diet estimation	carnivore bone collagen (‰ AIR N_2)		mean diet bone collagen (‰ AIR N_2)		collagen-to-collagen carnivore-diet trophic discriminations (‰ AIR N_2)		
		$\delta^{15}\text{N}_{\text{Glx}}$	$\delta^{15}\text{N}_{\text{Phe}}$	$\delta^{15}\text{N}_{\text{Glx}}$	$\delta^{15}\text{N}_{\text{Phe}}$	$\Delta^{15}\text{N}_{\text{Glx}}$	$\Delta^{15}\text{N}_{\text{Phe}}$	$\text{TDF}_{\text{Glx-Phe}}$
wolf	W1	11.2 ± 0.2	6.4 ± 0.2	6.8 ± 0.1	6.9 ± 0.1	4.4 ± 0.2	-0.4 ± 0.2	4.8 ± 0.3
wolf	W2	11.2 ± 0.2	6.4 ± 0.2	7.0 ± 0.1	7.2 ± 0.1	4.2 ± 0.2	-0.8 ± 0.2	5.0 ± 0.3
wolf	W3	11.2 ± 0.2	6.4 ± 0.2	6.6 ± 0.1	6.4 ± 0.1	4.6 ± 0.2	0.0 ± 0.2	4.6 ± 0.3
hyena	H1	13.3 ± 0.1	11.3 ± 0.2	8.7 ± 0.1	11.5 ± 0.1	4.6 ± 0.1	-0.3 ± 0.3	4.9 ± 0.3
hyena	H2	13.3 ± 0.1	11.3 ± 0.2	8.7 ± 0.1	11.4 ± 0.1	4.7 ± 0.1	-0.1 ± 0.3	4.8 ± 0.3

4.2. Problem of the β value variability

The β value (defined as a difference between $\delta^{15}\text{N}_{\text{Glx}}$ and $\delta^{15}\text{N}_{\text{Phe}}$ values in plants) have a profound impact on the $\delta^{15}\text{N}_{\text{Glx}}-\delta^{15}\text{N}_{\text{Phe}}$ relationship in herbivores (Ramirez et al., 2021) and is commonly used as a key parameter in the TP calculations (Ohkouchi, 2023). In paleoecological studies, the value of -8.4‰ is commonly accepted (Choy et al., 2024; Naito et al., 2020; Naito et al., 2016b; Nakashita et al., 2011). However, the β values are highly variable and may range among the terrestrial plants between -10.6‰ and $+0.1\text{‰}$ (these numbers represent means \pm SD for taxonomic groups shown in (Ramirez et al., 2021), but the entire min.-max. Range is even wider). The extreme theoretical TPs, modeled by the same authors for this β range, differs by as much as 4, which makes the TP estimation based on unknown but arbitrarily adopted β value unreliable (Larsen et al., 2022).

Our two datasets of Białowieża forest and Perspektywiczna Cave hyena den showed that the $\delta^{15}\text{N}_{\text{Glx}}-\delta^{15}\text{N}_{\text{Phe}}$ regressions in herbivores differ between two ecosystems (Fig. 1; significant ANCOVA for equality of slopes: $F = 79.98$, $P_{\text{same}} = 2.057 \cdot 10^{-10}$). This clearly points toward different Glx/Phe isotopic ratios in producers resulting in different β values, and undermines the concept of applying an arbitrarily chosen β value for an ecosystem that it was not tested for. In the following section we propose a TP estimation model that is independent of the β parameter.

4.3. New model for calculating TP

Eq. 2 is commonly used to estimate the TP. However, our results raised serious concerns about its usability. These regard the β value (should the baseline be plants?) and the TDF (should we use the same TDF for all TP levels?).

Martínez Del Rio et al. (2009) suggested to use herbivores as the baseline level for the TP calculation, instead of plants. Similar approach was also used by other studies (Karlson et al., 2024; Post, 2002). It is especially rational in the case of collagen-based studies. This is because the TDF for herbivores (TP 1 to TP 2) is estimated in a different way than the TDF for carnivores (higher TPs). The herbivores' TDF, or plant-to-herbivore TDF, is based on a bulk plant protein pool and a herbivore collagen's protein pool; in contrast, higher TPs' TDFs (herbivore-to-carnivore, or carnivore-to-carnivore) are based on collagen protein pools at both TPs (Bocherens and Drucker, 2003; Krajcarz et al., 2025; Krajcarz et al., 2018, 2019). Accounting for the offset between the $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ values of the collagen and other tissues or the entire body (Dalerum and Angerbjörn, 2005; Stephens et al., 2023), TDFs calculated in such a way for herbivory and carnivory would likely have different numerical values (schematically depicted in Fig. 2: A), further impacted by different diet qualities, i.e., the protein content in diet (Larsen et al., 2022; Whiteman et al., 2021). Such theoretical differences between TDFs at different TPs were detected in practice, e.g., by Germain et al. (2013). This points toward questioning the validity of Eq. 2 for $\text{TP} > 2$, in particular in collagen-based studies, where it would underestimate the TP of carnivores and omnivores (Fig. 2: B).

Fig. 1. Glutamate-phenylalanine relationships between the studied mammalian carnivores and their prey. Results for Białowieża Forest modern wolf are shown in A) and for Perspektywiczna Cave Pleistocene cave hyena in B). Vertical and horizontal distances between the carnivore mean (+) and its diet mean (×) represent the trophic discriminations in Glx and Phe ($\Delta^{15}N_{Glx}$ and $\Delta^{15}N_{Phe}$, respectively). Green solid lines, marked as TP 2, are linear regressions for all herbivores (wild boar excluded due to its omnivory) that demark a trophic level of herbivores within an ecosystem and thus represent the TP 2. Red solid lines are the TP 3 representations, which are obtained by shifting green lines up and right by $\Delta^{15}N_{Glx}$ and $\Delta^{15}N_{Phe}$ values, accordingly. The mean diets and TP 3 lines are shown for models W1 and H1; for other models see Figs. S4 and S5. Dashed grey lines (marked TP 2* and TP 3*) show the TP 2 and TP 3 according to Eq. (2) based on Chikaraishi et al. (2010, 2011). (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

Fig. 2. Schematic depiction of isotopic relationships between TPs based on TDFs for different tissues. Panel A) shows an effect of different isotopic spacing between TPs due to the difference between the herbivore’s TDF (marked as ‘general TDF’ and representing an isotopic shift between the plant entire protein pool and consumer’s bone collagen), and the carnivore’s TDF (marked as ‘coll.-to-coll. TDF’ and representing an isotopic shift between prey’s bone collagen and consumer’s bone collagen). Panels B) and C) show simulations of the TP estimation for a theoretical animal with use of different approaches: in B), all TPs are depicted with the same general TDF above the plant baseline (traditional model based on Chikaraishi et al., 2010, 2011); this leads to the underestimation of an animal’s TP when collagen isotopic data are used; in C), the TPs > 2 are based on collagen-to-collagen TDF above the herbivore level (the TP 2 baseline); this approach provides higher and correct TP for the collagen data.

We therefore propose a modified TP calculation approach that includes herbivore collagen baseline (Fig. 2: C, instead of plant baseline). In this model, the baseline is the mathematic representation of herbivores $\delta^{15}\text{N}_{\text{Glx}}-\delta^{15}\text{N}_{\text{Phe}}$ relationship in a form of linear regression ($y = ax + b$) of all studied herbivores' $\delta^{15}\text{N}_{\text{Glx}}-\delta^{15}\text{N}_{\text{Phe}}$ paired data. This regression follows the formula:

$$\delta^{15}\text{N}_{\text{Glx}} = a_h \delta^{15}\text{N}_{\text{Phe}} - b_h \quad (3)$$

where a_h and b_h are slope and intercept of the regression. The TP is then calculated as the position of a specimen's collagen $\delta^{15}\text{N}_{\text{Glx}}-\delta^{15}\text{N}_{\text{Phe}}$ datapoint above the herbivore collagen $\delta^{15}\text{N}_{\text{Glx}}-\delta^{15}\text{N}_{\text{Phe}}$ regression line, divided by the collagen-to-collagen TDF_{Glx-Phe}, according to the formula:

$$\text{TP} = \frac{\left(\delta^{15}\text{N}_{\text{Glx}} \frac{\text{TDF}_{\text{Phe}} \delta^{15}\text{N}_{\text{Glx}} - \delta^{15}\text{N}_{\text{Phe}} \frac{b_h}{a_h}}{\text{TDF}_{\text{Glx}}} - \left(\delta^{15}\text{N}_{\text{Phe}} \frac{\text{TDF}_{\text{Glx}} \delta^{15}\text{N}_{\text{Phe}} - \delta^{15}\text{N}_{\text{Glx}} + b_h}{\text{TDF}_{\text{Phe}}} \right) \frac{\text{TDF}_{\text{Glx}} - a_h}{\text{TDF}_{\text{Phe}}} \right)}{\text{TDF}_{\text{Glx-Phe}}} + 2 \quad (4)$$

where TDF_{Glx}, TDF_{Glx} and TDF_{Glx-Phe} are the collagen-to-collagen Glx, Phe and Glx-Phe TDFs, respectively, and + 2 is to anchor the formula at the TP 2 (i.e., at the baseline that is the herbivore's TP). The design of the Eq. 4 is presented in detail in the Supplementary Text.

4.4. Limitations of applying collagen-to-collagen TDF

We summarized the pros and cons for using our model in Table 2. The main advantage of this new model is that it correctly estimates the TP for collagen data of specimens of TP > 2, that was overestimated in the traditional model based on non-collagen data from Chikaraishi et al. (2010, 2011). Our model does not need isotopic data for plants, which is another advantage in paleoecological applications, because plant remains are usually scarce in the fossil record (Boeskorov et al., 2016). It does, however, need isotopic data for herbivores, and this calls for additional research material and requires arbitrary assumptions about those animals being herbivores. These problems can be, however, easily addressed in most of the archaeological and paleontological mammalian assemblages.

A downside of the proposed model is that being based on the herbivore baseline and having the plant-to-herbivore TDF not included,

Table 2

Strengths and weaknesses of the traditional model (Chikaraishi et al., 2010, 2011) and our proposed model of the TP estimation based on bone collagen $\delta^{15}\text{N}_{\text{Glx}}$ and $\delta^{15}\text{N}_{\text{Phe}}$ data.

Potential problems	Traditional model (Eq. 2)	Our model (Eq. 4)
plant isotopic values	β value is needed	not needed
β value uncertainty	profound impact on the model	not relevant
herbivore isotopic values	not needed	needed for baseline (typical requirements for linear regression, such as data independency, normality, and homoscedasticity, may be violated in some cases due to diversely selective diet of herbivore taxa)
TP 1 estimation	correct (assuming the β value is correct)	overestimated
TP 2 estimation	correct (assuming the β and TDF _{Glx-Phe} values are correct)	correct (assuming that all animals included in the herbivore baseline calculation were truly herbivorous)
TP > 2 estimation	overestimated	correct (assuming the herbivore baseline and collagen-to-collagen TDF _{Glx-Phe} value are correct)

our model would overestimate the TP of plants, likely placing them between TP 1 and TP 2. While this is a weakness, the model is not meant to be used for plants and it should not be applied for estimating the TP of plants. We also do not recommend it for studies of fungi, invertebrates, or any non-collagen vertebrate material.

4.5. Implementation of the new model in practice

We applied our model based on Eq. 4 for exemplary Pleistocene collagen $\delta^{15}\text{N}_{\text{Glx}}-\delta^{15}\text{N}_{\text{Phe}}$ data (Drucker et al., 2017) that included herbivores (including saiga, red deer, and hare) and ancient hominins remains excavated from the same archaeological context, i.e., the Upper Paleolithic layers 6-1 and 6-2 of the Buran-Kaya III site in Crimea, Ukraine. The herbivore $\delta^{15}\text{N}_{\text{Glx}}$ and $\delta^{15}\text{N}_{\text{Phe}}$ data reported in that study had acceptable linear fit (Pearson linear correlation $P_{\text{uncorr.}} < 0.004$, $R^2 = 0.7761$, maximum residual value 1.14, $P_{\text{homoscedastic}} = 0.62$). That allowed for reliable determination of the TP 2 baseline as the linear regression for all herbivores reported in that dataset. We applied the averaged of all our models (Table 1) TDF_{Glx-Phe} value of +4.8 %.

Our TP determinations revealed the trophic level of Buran-Kaya III human individuals being around TP = 3 and being higher by +0.4 to +0.5 from the previously determined TPs on the basis of Eq. 2 (Table 3). The difference in TP estimations between these two models gets larger with higher TPs; for herbivores the difference is neglected, but for a TP > 3 canid it gets as high as 0.7 (supplementary Table S8). Our results suggested higher level of carnivory in Crimean Upper Paleolithic humans than previously interpreted and highlighted the necessity of recalculation of previously published TPs based on collagen data.

4.6. Conclusive remarks

Our study evidenced that the collagen-to-collagen TDF_{Glx-Phe} was around $+4.8 \pm 0.1$ ‰ in mammalian carnivorans, confirmed independently in two prey-predator assemblages and in several models of prey composition. This is much lower than the value of +7.6 ‰, proposed earlier on the basis of plants, insectivores and fish analysis (Chikaraishi et al., 2009, 2010, 2011) and applied in previous studies (Choy et al., 2024; Jaouen et al., 2019; Naito et al., 2016a; Naito et al., 2016b; Nakashita et al., 2011). Importantly, this new TDF value significantly alters TP estimations, as exemplified in the Late Pleistocene hominins from the Buran-Kaya III site. Because among the input data used for the TDF estimation was herbivore collagen $\delta^{15}\text{N}_{\text{Glx}}$ and $\delta^{15}\text{N}_{\text{Phe}}$ values, it is rational to use such a TP estimation model that adopts herbivore collagen as the food web mathematical baseline. We proposed such a model (our Eq. 4), which is a modification of Chikaraishi et al.'s (2009, 2010, 2011) model. As long as the plant $\delta^{15}\text{N}_{\text{Glx}}$ and $\delta^{15}\text{N}_{\text{Phe}}$ values in ancient ecosystems stay unknown and the plant-to-mammal herbivore's collagen TDF is unknown, we strongly advise the application of our model (Eq. 4) for terrestrial mammalian collagen-based studies.

Table 3

Comparison of exemplary previous TP estimations and new TP estimations based on our model. The TP estimation is presented for Upper Paleolithic humans (*Homo sapiens*) from Buran-Kaya III cave in Crimean Peninsula, Ukraine (data from Drucker et al., 2017). Previous TP estimations after the same authors are based on Eq. 2 using the plant baseline with hypothetical β value of -8.4 ‰ and TDF_{Glx-Phe} of +7.6 ‰. Our new TP estimations are based on our model (Eq. 4) and use herbivore collagen data from the same archaeological context as the baseline and TDF_{Glx-Phe} of +4.8 ‰ (for calculations see the supplementary Table S8).

Specimen	Previous TP estimation (according to Eq. 2)	New TP estimation (according to Eq. 4)
BK3-07-01	2.6	3.1
BK3-12-01	2.5	3.0
BK3-11-01	2.5	2.9

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Maciej T. Krajcarz: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Magdalena Krajcarz:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Resources, Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Rafał Kowalczyk:** Writing – review & editing, Resources. **Peter Tung:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation, Formal analysis. **Hervé Bocherens:** Writing – review & editing, Resources, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare the following financial interests/personal relationships which may be considered as potential competing interests:

Magdalena Krajcarz reports financial support was provided by Horizon Europe Excellent Science. Maciej T. Krajcarz reports financial support was provided by National Agency for Academic Exchange. If there are other authors, they declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.palaeo.2025.113040>.

Data availability

Data available from the Zenodo digital repository <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14795699>.

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